

AN ANALYSIS OF THE NEUTRALISATION CURVES OF THE COLLOIDAL ACIDS. PART VI

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It is shown that the conductometric neutralisation curves for the colloidal clay acids can be constructed theoretically which compare favourably with experimental, from a knowledge of the counterions obtained by p_n and a_n determinations. It has been suggested that these colloidal electrolytes are of the uni-univalent type and some of the special characteristics attributed to the double layers surrounding the particles for the interpretation of the conductometric neutralisation curves are unnecessary.

In previous communications (Gupta, Parts I-V, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 587; 1957, 34, 63, 691, 696, 743) it has been shown that the curves for p_n , a_n and specific conductivity, during the neutralisation of colloidal acids, against concentration of added base are related, and if the curves happen to be of the theoretical type viz., Bradfield type (Part V, *loc. cit.*) then it is possible to predict the a_n curve (Part III, *loc. cit.*) or the specific conductivity curve (Part II, *loc. cit.*) from the p_n curve alone by evaluating a series of dissociation constants. For curves of the irregular type, as obtained by Marshall, which do not fit in with any of the equations for reasons discussed earlier (Part V, *loc. cit.*), two curves, i. e., p_n and a_n , are necessary to predict the third curve, i. e., the specific conductivity curve. The present communication seeks to demonstrate this fact with already published informations on the neutralisation of some clay acids.

The necessary experimental data, presented here for the purpose of evaluation and comparison, have been obtained from the works of Marshall and Krinbill (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1942, 46, 1077). The data consist of values of p_n , a_n and specific conductivity during the neutralisation of acid clay suspensions of each of the four clay minerals, Beidellite, Montmorillonite, Illite and Kaolinite, with increasing addition of the titrating alkali, i. e., NaOH. In the same paper the authors have calculated the cationic contribution to the total conductance and have shown that there remains a gap between the two values ascribed to the anionic contribution, which becomes wider as the titration proceeds. The present calculations show that the gap can be effectively closed if the anionic contributions are added to those of the cations. For the computation of the specific conductivity, the equation employed is

$$\kappa = \frac{U_{n+}(a_{n+})_t + U_{n-}(a_{n-})_t + V_{OH-}(a_{OH-})_t + V_{n-}(a_{n+} + a_{n-} - a_{OH-})_t}{1000}$$

where the symbols have their usual significances (note the misprint of this equation in Part IV, *loc. cit.*). In the above equation V_{n-} , it will be remembered, represents the limiting conductance of the clay particles per equivalent of charge on the clay surface and the amount of charge in equivalents is given by $(a_{n+} + a_{n-} - a_{OH-})_t$. The following values have been assumed: $U_{n+} = 50.11$, $U_{n-} = 349.82$, and $V_{OH-} = 198.5$ mhos $\text{cm}^3 \text{equiv.}^{-1}$ respectively at 25°. The values of V_{n-} necessary to give a good fit had to be obtained by trial for each of the four clay minerals. Thus, it has been found that the following values of V_{n-} in mhos $\text{cm}^3 \text{equiv.}^{-1}$ fit the data satisfactorily: 35 for Beidellite, 40 for Montmorillonite, 55 for Illite and 60 for Kaolinite.

TABLE I
 Puffnam clay (Beidellite), fraction $< 0.2\mu$. Anionic conductance ≈ 35 mhos cm^2 equiv. ¹.
 'b' NaOH (moles/litre). ρ_{21} .

'b' NaOH (moles/litre).	ρ_{21} .	$(a_{Na^+})_t$.	$(a_{OH^-})_t$.	$(a_{Na^+})_t$.	$(a_{OH^-})_t$.	Anionic conductance ≈ 35 mhos cm^2 equiv. ¹ .		Thixotropic setting time.
						Calc.	Obs.	
0.00×10^{-3}	3.80	$0.00 \times 10^{-3}N$	$1.585 \times 10^{-4}N$	10% Suspension	$0.1585 \times 10^{-3}N$	0.61×10^{-4}	0.622×10^{-4}	
1.04	5.27	1.07	5.37×10^{-5}		1.075	0.93	1.25	
2.08	5.52	1.86	3.02×10^{-5}		1.86	1.59	1.92	
3.13	5.57	3.62	2.69×10^{-5}		3.62	3.08	3.26	0 sec.
6.8	7.00	11.9		Negligible.	11.9	10.12	...	0
7.3	8.09	14.3		$1.23 \times 10^{-6}N$	14.3	12.19	8.9	72
7.82	8.95	15.0		8.91×10^{-6}	15.0	12.77	10.3	
9.4	10.58	24.6		3.80×10^{-4}	24.2	21.50	18.8	
11.5	11.44	35.7		2.75×10^{-3}	32.95	34.90	39.9	
0.00×10^{-1}	3.83	$0.00 \times 10^{-3}N$	$1.47 \times 10^{-4}N$	7% Suspension.	$0.148 \times 10^{-3}N$	0.565×10^{-4}	0.656×10^{-4}	
0.361	4.77	...	1.70×10^{-5}		...	...	1.520	
0.721	5.44	0.87	3.63×10^{-6}		0.87	0.752	0.916	
1.44	5.70	1.42	2.00×10^{-6}		1.40	1.27	1.37	
2.16	5.75	2.32	1.78×10^{-6}		2.32	1.98	2.02	
2.88	5.75	3.32	1.78×10^{-6}		3.32	2.81	2.91	30 min.
3.61	6.03	4.22	9.33×10^{-7}		4.22	3.59	3.32	6
3.96	6.20	5.06			5.06	4.34		0
4.22	6.54	5.37			5.37	4.57	4.31	15
4.68	7.03	6.03		Negligible	6.03	5.10	4.73	
5.05	8.08	7.93		$1.20 \times 10^{-6}N$	7.93	6.75	6.12	
5.40	8.94	8.77		8.71×10^{-6}	8.76	7.46	6.44	
6.48	10.54	14.00		3.47×10^{-4}	13.66	12.48	12.20	
7.93	11.35	23.50		2.24×10^{-3}	21.66	24.00	27.00	

TABLE II
Bentonite (Montmorillonite), fraction <math> < 0.2 \mu </math>. Anionic conductance = 40 mhos cm^2 equiv.⁻¹.

H^+NaOH (moles/litre)	ϕ_2	$(a_{\text{M}^+})_t$	$(a_{\text{H}^+})_t$	$(a_{\text{OH}^-})_t$	$(a_{\text{M}^+} + a_{\text{H}^+} - a_{\text{OH}^-})_t$	Sp. cond. (mhos)		Thixotropy.
						Calc.	Obs.	
0.002×10^{-3}	2.87	$0.00 \times 10^{-3}N$	$1.35 \times 10^{-3}N$	$1.35 \times 10^{-3}N$	$1.35 \times 10^{-3}N$	5.26×10^{-4}	4.15×10^{-4}	
0.142	3.23	...	5.89×10^{-4}	...	...	...	2.91	
0.425	4.09	1.75	8.13×10^{-5}	1.83	1.83	2.09	2.16	
0.994	5.08	2.56	8.32×10^{-6}	2.57	2.57	2.34	2.64	
1.56	5.33	4.17	4.67×10^{-6}	4.17	4.17	3.77	3.35	
1.99	5.66	5.45	2.19×10^{-6}	5.45	5.45	4.91	4.31	Present
2.27	5.88	5.47	1.32×10^{-6}	5.47	5.47	4.93	4.15	Maximum
2.41	6.02	5.63		5.63	5.63	5.07	4.31	Present
2.55	6.73	6.47		6.47	6.47	5.88	4.73	
2.69	7.30	8.73		8.73	8.73	7.86	5.11	
2.84	8.24	10.80		10.80	10.80	9.73	6.04	
3.12	9.51	12.20		12.17	12.17	11.00	7.18	
3.41	10.07	14.80		14.70	14.70	13.50	8.95	
3.97	11.10	19.00		17.74	17.74	19.00	15.70	
0.000×10^{-3}	3.23	$0.00 \times 10^{-3}N$	$5.89 \times 10^{-4}N$	$0.589 \times 10^{-3}N$	$0.589 \times 10^{-3}N$	2.29×10^{-4}	2.17×10^{-4}	
0.151	4.30	0.48	5.01×10^{-5}	0.53	0.53	0.63	1.08	
0.553	5.88	1.20	1.32×10^{-5}	1.20	1.20	1.10	1.23	
0.803	6.35	1.49	4.47×10^{-7}	1.49	1.49	1.34	1.43	
0.853	6.43	1.55		1.55	1.55	1.40	1.43	
0.904	6.75	1.70		1.70	1.70	1.53	1.60	
0.954	7.08	1.95		1.95	1.95	1.76	1.85	
1.100	8.99	2.76		2.75	2.75	2.49	2.48	
1.210	9.69	3.37		3.32	3.32	3.11	3.12	
1.410	10.57	5.30		4.93	4.93	5.37	5.52	

2.8% Suspension.

Negligible

 $1.74 \times 10^{-5}N$ 3.24×10^{-5} 1.18×10^{-4} 1.26×10^{-3}

1.0% Suspension.

Negligible

 $9.77 \times 10^{-5}N$ 4.90×10^{-5} 3.72×10^{-4}

TABLE III
 Illinois "grundite", (Illite), fraction $< 2\mu$. f -ionic conductance = 55 mbos cm^2 equiv. $^{-1}$.

"b" NaOH (moles/litre).	pH.	$(a_{\text{Na}^+})_t$.	$(a_{\text{H}^+})_t$.	$(a_{\text{OH}^-})_t$.	10% Suspension.	Sp. cond. (mbos).	
						Calc.	Obs.
0.0×10^{-3}	3.49	$0.00 \times 10^{-3}N$	$3.436 \times 10^{-4}N$	3.98×10^{-8}	$3.236 \times 10^{-4}N$	1.1×10^{-5}	7.68×10^{-5}
5.2	5.40	0.557	3.98×10^{-8}	1.82×10^{-8}	5.61	6.01	5.74
8.3	5.74	0.663	1.82×10^{-8}	1.00×10^{-8}	6.65	7.04	6.65
12.5	6.00	0.928	1.00×10^{-8}		9.29	9.74	8.33
16.7	6.22	1.41			12.1	12.7	10.6
20.8	6.54	1.49			14.9	15.6	12.3
25.0	7.43	2.29			22.9	24.0	18.5
29.9	8.77	3.58			35.7	37.6	29.6
33.3	9.85	5.45			53.8	58.3	47.7
37.5	10.70	9.56			90.6	107.4	84.5
					Negligible		
					$5.89 \times 10^{-4}N$		
					7.08×10^{-3}		
					5.01×10^{-4}		
					5% Suspension.		
0.0×10^{-3}	3.71	$0.00 \times 10^{-3}N$	$1.08 \times 10^{-4}N$	$1.95 \times 10^{-4}N$	$1.95 \times 10^{-4}N$	7.89×10^{-5}	5.98×10^{-5}
2.55	5.58	0.238	2.63×10^{-4}	2.40	2.40	2.60	3.22
4.08	6.00	0.284	1.00×10^{-4}	2.84	2.84	2.98	3.65
6.12	6.27	0.361	5.37×10^{-4}	3.61	3.61	3.79	4.37
8.15	6.49	0.473		4.73	4.73	4.97	5.48
10.20	6.79	0.594		5.94	5.94	6.22	6.50
12.20	7.48	0.899		8.99	8.99	9.45	9.73
14.30	8.62	1.430		14.30	$4.17 \times 10^{-6}N$	15.10	15.80
15.30	9.52	2.280		22.50	3.31×10^{-5}	27.30	26.20
18.40	10.26	3.690		35.10	1.82×10^{-4}	41.40	45.20

TABLE IV
 Kaolinite, fraction $< 2\mu$. Anionic conductance = 60 mhos cm^2 equiv. $^{-1}$

'b' NaOH (moles/litre)	p_H	$(a_{H^+})_t$	$(a_{H^+})_f$	$(a_{OH^-})_t$	$(a_{OH^-})_f$	10% Suspension	$(a_{H^+} + a_{H^+} - a_{OH^-})_t$	Calc.	Sp cond. (mhos).	
									Calc.	Obs.
0.00×10^{-3}	4.62	$0.00 \times 10^{-4}N$	$2.40 \times 10^{-5}N$				$0.24 \times 10^{-4}N$	0.170×10^{-4}	0.113×10^{-4}	
0.52	6.03	2.20	9.33×10^{-7}				2.20	0.228	0.269	
1.04	6.35	2.88	4.47×10^{-7}				2.88	0.319	0.370	
2.08	6.67	4.98					4.98	0.549	0.625	
3.12	7.91	10.50					10.50	1.160	1.250	
4.16	9.75	18.10				$5.62 \times 10^{-5}N$	17.54	2.070	2.020	
5.20	10.34	26.30				2.19×10^{-4}	24.11	3.400	3.200	
6.24	10.70	34.70				5.01×10^{-4}	29.69	4.500	4.700	
7.28	10.95	43.60				8.91×10^{-4}	34.69	6.030	6.500	

FIG. 2

FIG. 1

In the previous publications of this series, for the calculation of the specific conductivity of a clay sample (Part II, *loc. cit.*), and for the AgI sol (Part IV, *loc. cit.*) we used such values of anionic conductance for the charge on colloid surface. The present experimental fits, it is hoped, will strengthen such belief in the reality of the quantity. The results are presented in Tables I, II, III and IV and the calculated and observed values of the specific conductivities on 7th and 8th columns of the tables. For convenience of comparison the values are also shown graphically in Figs. 1 to 4.

It will be seen from the results that the calculated values of specific conductivity are more or less in complete agreement with the experimental ones in the case of the dilute suspensions for the whole range of titration for all the clay minerals, while in the case of relatively concentrated suspensions, the calculated specific conductivity values are somewhat higher. This may be due to our assumption of the limiting value of the ionic conductance for each of the ionic species, while, in fact, the values have to be reduced for concentrated suspensions according to the interionic attraction theory. A better fit might have been obtained by introducing the Onsager correction, but this could not be done as the said correction is on the basis of stoichiometric concentrations for strong electrolytes and not for electrochemically determined activities. The above consideration holds good particularly for Bentonite and Illite and it also holds good for Reidellite except for the last point. The calculated and experimental curves cross as the final calculated value is lower than the experimental for the curves of the last named clay mineral.

In the case of 1% Bentonite sample (Fig. 2), the second point is unusually low, causing some deviation in the initial stage between the calculated and the experimental curves. It will be seen from the data that for all other samples, the charge on the clay surface, given by figures in the 6th column of the tables, increases continuously from the beginning of the neutralisation as the neutralisation proceeds. This is demanded by the theory of weak acid neutralisation of clay suspensions (Part II, *loc. cit.*). In this particular case of 1% Bentonite, however, there is a diminution of particle charge at the second point. It seems that the recorded p_n value for this point is somewhat high. A slightly lower p_n value will bring this point in line with the experimental curve for specific conductivity. This is likely because this point falls on the initial rising part of the p_n curve where the clay sample may be considered to be highly unbuffered. A slight discrepancy of initial p_n reading seems also to exist in the case of Illite samples.

It is interesting to note, as pointed out by Marshall *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), that the region of thixotropy in 10% and 7% Beidellite and the 2.8% Bentonite is not characterised by any change in the conditions of conductance, as shown in these experiments. This confirms for the case of clays what has long been established for soaps by McDain, namely, "that the mechanism of conductance is not essentially different in gels from what it is in sols". This observation is important as it points to the difficulty of correlating viscosity measurements with neutralisation and also to the fact that the counter ions are obstructed in no way by thixotropic gelation.

FIG. 3

It is apparent from the above analysis that the anionic conductance per equivalent of charge is highest in the case of Kaolinite and least in the case of Beidellite, the order being Kaolinite $>$ Illite $>$ Montmorillonite $>$ Beidellite. The anionic conductances of Kaolinite and Illite clays are even greater than Na^+ ions.

Several irresistible conclusions present themselves from the above agreement as

FIG. 4

well as from our previous analyses of the neutralisation curves of other sols (Parts I-V, *loc. cit.*). These colloidal electrolytes are fundamentally of uni-univalent type, as pointed out by the McBain from a study of their soap solutions (cf. McBain, "Colloid Science", 1950, D. C. Heath & Co., p. 255; Gupta, *Science & Culture*, 1957-58, 23, 103, 493), and it is possible to deal with these from classical standpoint without having to take recourse to some of the double layer characteristics. For example, the double layer theory holds that there is a gradation of binding strength between

the cations of the double layer and the colloid surface which falls off with increasing distance from the wall. The cations nearer to the wall are more firmly bound and in the limit form a layer of adsorbed ions. Secondly, it assumes that because of this unequal binding strength, the conductance of the small ions is greater in the periphery and outside of the double layer than near to the surface (cf. Kruyt, "Colloid Science", Part I, 1950, Elsevier Publishing Co., p. 179). Thirdly, the demarcation line separa-

ting the double layer from the intermicellar liquid is not clearly set, for example, one cannot say which part of the small ions belongs to the double layer and which part to the intermicellar solution (cf. Kruyt, *loc. cit.*, pp. 238-240). The present study shows that such assumptions are unnecessary. The adsorbed cations given by $a(a_{Na^+})_s$ and $(a_{Na^+})_s$ (Part I, *loc. cit.*), which are situated at an inner surface (Gupta, *Science & Culture*, 1957, 22, 512; 1958, 23, 366) do not contribute to the conductivity at all, while the free ions given by $(a_{Na^+})_l$, $(a_{OH^-})_l$ and $(a_{Cl^-})_l$ contribute fully to the total conductivity just as in a solution of any uni-univalent electrolyte. The deviation for concentrated suspensions is due to causes dealt with by interionic attraction theory, and the Onsager correction becoming significant. Evidently, the reason for our assumption is, as has been repeatedly pointed out by McBain (*loc. cit.*), that the charges on the surface of the colloidal particles are so far apart that they have the properties of a uni-univalent electrolyte as if present in true solution. The prerequisite of assuming gradation of binding strength is to consider that the whole charge on a particle is concentrated at a central point within the particle, ignoring the large surface on which they are distributed, which picture is likely to be far from the real state of affairs.

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